

Autonomous SDN-based Global Concurrent Restoration for High-Capacity Optical Metro Networks

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Abstract: The full integration of an OAM function with a SDN controller to support autonomic networking capabilities within optical metro networks is presented. A devised Global Concurrent RSA algorithm to maximize connection restorability is experimentally evaluated. © 2021 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

To cope with the huge transport capacity (Tb/s), dynamic, and flexible bandwidth provisioning for 5G and B5G traffic, optical metro networks segment become crucial. These networks are designed to be efficient in terms of cost and energy, and to support *autonomic* networking capabilities for re-optimization and reliability purposes [1]. In the EU-H2020 PASSION project, those metro network challenges are approached by combining photonic technologies with SDN programmable and adaptive transport solutions [1][2]. Specifically, a modular multi-flow sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT) exploiting vertical cavity surface emitting laser (VCSEL) sources has emerged as a promising solution to reduce cost, power, and footprint [1].

The *autonomic* network feature in dynamic metro network scenarios is of paramount importance [3]. This entails gathering monitored information from the established connections and leveraging this to recommend the SDN framework to carry out actions (e.g., re-computation or restoration) targeting the continuous fulfilment of the service needs. This work tackles the implementation of an Operational, Administration and Maintenance (OAM) element to accomplish a full autonomous SDN control system. The integration of the SDN controller and the OAM element focuses on the dynamic connection restoration upon a (predicted) network anomaly. Besides detailing the SDN controller-OAM interactions (via a defined REST API), a Global Concurrent Restoration (GCR) Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) is devised. The GCR RSA algorithm aims at effectively restoring active optical connections/LSPs disrupted by a single network anomaly (e.g., link failure). The GCR RSA algorithm is experimentally evaluated in the ADRENALINE tested. The experimental setup deploys a metro network scenario with full-fledged control functions (i.e., SDN controller, OAM, RSA algorithms, and device agents for S-BVTs and optical switches), whilst the data plane is emulated. The evaluation is done in terms of four metrics: blocked bandwidth ratio (BBR), average setup delay, restorability, and average restoration time.

2. Autonomic Networking: SDN Controller and OAM Integration

Fig. 1.(a) depicts the SDN controller-OAM integration to support autonomic networking functions: S0) the regular allocation of new incoming optical connections specifying the source node (*src*), destination node (*dst*) and data rate (*bw*); S1) the collection of monitored information of established LSPs; S2) the training and testing mechanisms of machine learning (ML) models to e.g., predict network anomalies; S3) the processing of network anomalies (e.g., link failure); S4) the re-computation of affected LSPs by a network anomaly. Herein, we focus on the S0, S3 and S4 operations: LSP provisioning and restoration.

New optical connections arrive to the SDN controller, which triggers a provisioning RSA algorithm [2]. This algorithm seeks for a feasible path fulfilling the connection bandwidth demands and ensuring underlying technological constraints (e.g., spectrum continuity and contiguity). It is worth outlining that a connection may require more than one Frequency Slot (FS) to be computed by the RSA and then provisioned. The reason behind this is that in the adopted modular S-BVT, each VCSEL source element operates at a fixed wavelength providing up to 50 Gb/s. Thus, if the *bw* is larger than 50 Gb/s (e.g., 200 Gb/s), different VCSELs are allocated deriving in different FSs. A successfully computed LSP is described by: i) the S-BVT Tx (VCSELs) and Coherent Receivers (Co-Rxs) resources to be allocated at *src* and *dst*, respectively; ii) the spatial path (i.e., nodes and links); and iii) the spectral resources (i.e., FSs). Moreover, the RSA algorithm considers that the received *net* data rate at the *dst* may be lower than 50 Gb/s due to the accumulated signal degradation. Consequently, three different VCSEL operational modes (OMs), namely *high*, *medium* and *low*, providing diverse data rates, are defined [2]. Each OM's data rate is bound to

both a maximum path distance (in km) and number of traversed hops, see Fig. 1(c). The RSA objective function is thus to find the path and the optical resources that minimizes both the total end-to-end distance and number of hops.

Fig. 1. (a) SDN Controller – OAM Interworking; (b) Optical Metro Netw. Scenario; (c) VCSEL operation modes

As said, the OAM tackles the actions upon an arising network anomaly. This encompasses three functions: i) determining the set of affected LSPs (i.e., *failedLSPs*); ii) the path and resource re-computation, iii) the allocation triggering of the computed LSPs via the SDN controller. To do that, the OAM keeps a local duplication of both repositories: the connection database (DB) and the traffic engineering database (TED) When restoring *failedLSPs*, the OAM relies on a break-before-make (BBM) strategy where first all the *failedLSPs* are torn down, and then the devised GCR RSA algorithm is executed to accommodate such LSPs.

3. Proposed OAM Global Concurrent Restoration RSA Algorithm

The macroscopic objective of the GCR RSA algorithm is thus to compute a feasible spatial and spectral path for each LSP in the *failedLSPs* maximizing the restorability (i.e., $total_restored_bw / total_failed_bw$). The GCR RSA is based on the above provisioning RSA algorithm (*provRSA*) [2]. The inputs of the GCR RSA algorithm are the *failedLSPs* formed by N LSPs (i.e., $LSP_1, LSP_2, \dots, LSP_n$), and the gathered TED and S-BVT information queried to the SDN controller. For each LSP_i , having its own src_i, dst_i , and bw_i , the GCR RSA algorithm executes the *provRSA*. The *provRSA* computations are done following the LSP ordering in the *failedLSPs*. Thus, prior to compute the next LSP_{i+1} , those selected resources (i.e., S-BVT VCSELS and Co-Rxs, and optical spectrum link) used to accommodate the LSP_i are set to occupied in the OAM's TED instance. This does avoid double-booking the same resources among LSPs but the restorability success of the algorithm highly depends on the actual *failedLSPs* ordering. In other words, for a given *failedLSPs* there may be a specific ordering which allows attaining the highest restorability among those LSPs. To this end, the GCR RSA algorithm aims at exploring up to S ($S \leq N!$) solutions (i.e., S *provRSA* computations for each LSP) for a specific *failedLSPs*. Each s_i in S is computed shuffling/randomizing the LSP ordering. The final selected s_i is the one attaining the higher amount of *restored_bw*. If two or more solutions achieve the same *restored_bw*, the chosen s_i is the one restoring higher number of LSPs. If the tie holds, it is fostered the s_i leading to allocate lowest amount of FSs among all the restored LSPs. Random selection is finally applied if the tie between two or more s_i still holds.

4. SDN Control-OAM Entity Workflow Validation and Experimental Evaluation

Fig.2(a) depicts the SDN controller-OAM workflow to restore a *failedLSPs* set. This entails 6 steps: R1) OAM connection DB retrieval of active LSPs via REST GET method sent to the SDN controller; R2) determining the *failedLSPs*; R3) releasing the LSPs in *failedLSPs* (via REST DELETE method); R4) querying via REST GET method an update of the TED and S-BVT resources; R5) executing the GCR RSA algorithm; and finally, R6) requesting the programmability of the successfully computed LSPs sending a POST message to the SDN controller. Fig.2(b) illustrates the captured REST API packets exchanged between the OAM and the SDN controller. Additionally, it is shown the JSON contents carried in the POST message with the resources to be allocated for a successfully computed LSP: identifier, src , dst , bw . Importantly, the so-called *sero_list* details the specific resources to be configured: nodes, links, and ITU-T flexi-grid FSs (64bits) defining the central frequency (i.e., n) and slot width (i.e., m). This allows the SDN controller configuring the underlying optical network elements and devices (i.e., S-BVT VCSELS, Co-Rxs and optical switches).

The GCR RSA algorithm is experimentally evaluated upon both dynamic LSP arrival/departure, and network link failure events. The metro network topology (see Fig.1(c)) is deployed over the ADRENALINE testbed with 28

Linux-based servers hosting S-BVTs and optical switch agents, and two servers for both the SDN controller and the OAM entity. Each access-metro network node (labelled by 1-24) has an S-BVT with 20 VCSELs (spaced 100GHz) and Co-Rxs. Transit nodes 25-27 form a 3 node-ring network for optical transport and aggregation between the access-metro and the metro-core node (labelled by 28). Node 28 has 3 S-BVTs supporting 160 VCSELs (spaced 25GHz) and Co-Rxs each. Optical links have different distances with 645 central frequencies spaced 6.25 GHz. New LSPs arrive according to a Poisson process with mean inter-arrival time (IAT_p) of 5s. The LSP duration is modelled exponentially with a mean holding time (HT) of 400, 500 and 600s. 5k unidirectional LSPs connecting either access-metro nodes to metro-core node (and viceversa) are requested whose *bw* is uniformly distributed [50, 100, 150 and 200] Gb/s. Link failures occur exclusively within the 3-node ring using a Poisson process with an IAT_r set to 40s.

Fig. 2. (a) Workflow SDN Ctrl-OAM; (b) Packet capture of the restoration workflow; (c) Performance evaluation GCR RSA S=1 and 6. Fig.2.(c) shows the performance evaluation comparing the GCR RSA algorithm when for each *failedLPs* is computed a single solution (no shuffling), i.e., S=1, or adopting shuffling to derive up to 6 solutions (S=6). The performance metrics are the BBR, the average setup time (ST) in ms, the restorability, and the restoration time (RT) in ms. We observe that for low/medium traffic loads (i.e., low HT) increasing the number of explored solutions (i.e., S) by the GCR RSA algorithm, both the restorability and BBR are improved. For instance, for HT=400s, the BBR in S=1 is 0.08 whilst the same metric for S=6 results 0.065. For the restorability, S=1 achieves 0.86, whilst in S=6 this is 0.90. Indeed, as expected, S=6 fosters finding an existing solution that not only does enhance the restoration of larger amount of failed bandwidth, but also allows seeking for LSP paths which accomplish a more efficient use of the overall resources (i.e., lower amount of required S-BVT devices and FSs). This is done, however, at the expenses of increasing the restoration time due to higher computational time bound to a larger number of explored solutions. At high traffic load (HT=600s), both S=1 and S=6 performs similarly. Indeed, network resources tend to be notably occupied which severally constrains the number of feasible paths. Hence, exploring larger number of solutions by the GCR RSA algorithm does not bring an improvement in the targeted metrics.

5. Conclusions

This work presents the integration of the SDN controller and the OAM entity to support autonomic networking capabilities within optical metro networks. The workflow between both elements (via a defined REST API) is detailed. The objective is to autonomously handle network link failures affecting active LSPs. To this end, a GCR RSA algorithm is devised and experimentally evaluated upon dynamic traffic where two different number of explored solutions (S) are compared. We observe that at low/medium traffic loads using a higher number of S does increase the overall restorability and lower the BBR at the expenses of slightly increasing the restoration time.

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6. References

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